

Multibeam Sonar Backscatter Workshop (Backscatter Working Group – BSWG II)

Halifax, Nova Scotia, Canada. 25–27 October 2022

Dalhousie University, Halifax, Nova Scotia, Canada

**Conveners: Drs. Craig J. Brown (Dalhousie University, Canada),
Alexandre C. G. Schimel (NGU, Norway) and Marc Roche (FPS
Economy, Belgium)**

Workshop Summary Report

Multibeam Sonar Backscatter Workshop – (Backscatter Working Group – BSWG II)
Halifax, Nova Scotia, Canada. 25–27 October 2022
Hosted at Dalhousie University, Halifax, Nova Scotia, Canada

Conveners: Drs. Craig J. Brown (Dalhousie University, Canada), Alexandre C. G. Schimel (NGU, Norway)
and Marc Roche (FPS Economy, Belgium)

Summary:

A three-day international workshop on multibeam sonar backscatter was held (Oct. 25-27, 2022) at Dalhousie University (Halifax, Nova Scotia, Canada), coordinated by the Backscatter Working Group (BSWG) and with support from the Ocean Frontier Institute - Benthic Ecosystem Mapping and Engagement project (OFI BEcoME project – www.ofibecome.org). The workshop was attended by 57 delegates: 20 delegates attending onsite and 37 delegates attending online. The workshop served to continue and expand the BSWG activities, which aim at supporting improvements in the quality and consistency of multibeam backscatter data products. The overarching goals of the workshop were to:

- Present and share information on current backscatter research activities and projects that are underway
- Discuss the objectives, organization, and structure of the BSWG II – and how this group can help to progress the field of backscatter research
- Identify research opportunities and gaps in this field
- Develop a roadmap for future coordinated BSWG activities

Several actions have been decided for the future of the BSWG. This report provides a summary of the workshop, including main discussion items and future direction of the BSWG.

The agenda, presentation PDFs, collaborative notes, and event photos can be found in [the public BSWG Dropbox folder](#) (sub-folder “MEETINGS/BSWG workshop Halifax, Oct 2022”).

The recorded presentations can be found on [the BSWG YouTube channel](#).

Presentations (Day 1 and Day 2):

The workshop opened with some general comments and communication on the goals and objectives of the workshop. Context was provided on the progress that past multibeam backscatter workshops and research activities have achieved over the past two decades. On day one and the first session of day 2 of the workshop, invited presentations were made by delegates to outline current backscatter research activities, and present ideas on future research needs and ideas on the role that the BSWG could play in advancing this field of research.

The presentations are listed in Table 1 and 2. [The PDFs of all presentations have been posted online](#). The recordings of the presentations are available on [the BSWG YouTube channel](#).

Table 1: Day 1 presentations, authors, and titles

<i>Time</i>	<i>Presenter</i>	<i>Presentation title</i>
10:30	Craig Brown	Opening remarks and welcome Introductions and Housekeeping Goals and objectives of the workshop
11:30	Xavier Lurton	The Backscatter Working Group : A recap of Season 1 – toward Season 2! (Keynote presentation)
14:00	Vince Lecours	Identifying priority questions in acoustic backscatter research: preliminary results from community input
14:20	Ridha Fezzani	From data acquisition to seafloor characterization, IFREMER approach for absolute backscatter measurements and processing for various applications
14:40	Marc Roche	What scientific developments are needed to improve the use of the MBES backscatter for monitoring the impact of sand extraction in the Belgian part of the North Sea?
15:00	Tim LeBas	Use of Artificial Intelligence for interpretation when using backscatter imagery
15:20	Luciano Fonseca	Searching for polymetallic crusts and nodules in the Brazilian EEZ using backscatter physical models and echo statistics – preliminary results
15:40	Peter Urban	How can we boost the development and application of new scientific methods in the (water column) backscatter community?
16:30	Aniol Martí	A compression tool for the efficient browsing and transfer of water column backscatter data
16:50	Alexandre Schimel	CoFFee multibeam sonar data toolbox, and its applications for seafloor backscatter data quality analysis and water-column data processing
17:10	Peter Porskamp	Integrating multibeam echosounder water-column data into a benthic habitat mapping workflow
17:30	Pim Kuus	Seabat Normalised Backscatter
17:50	Mike Smith	Acoustic backscatter research at the Center for Coastal and Ocean Mapping: Where we are and where we are going
18:10	Miguel Candido	Particular complications in properly handling backscatter from multi-sector, multi-swath systems

Table 2: Day 2 presentations, authors, and titles

<i>Time</i>	<i>Presenter</i>	<i>Presentation title</i>
08:00	Samuel Deleu	Backscatter/Water Column data within the Belgian Hydrographic Office and ideas/suggestions for the future
08:20	Craig Brown	Multispectral backscatter for improved benthic habitat characterization
08:40	Ben Misiuk	Seabed characterization using multi-parameter and multi-source backscatter

9:00	Pedro Menandro	Multispectral Backscatter: advantages of using a multifrequency methodology for rhodolith mapping and an overview of ongoing projects that engage backscatter in Brazil
9:20	Jens Schneider	Interpretation difficulties in habitat backscatter mapping in the coastal white ribbon
9:40	Qian Bai	Using the Current Backscatter Technology for Seafloor Characterization

Discussion (Day 2):

Following the presentations in the first session of day 2, the remainder of the day comprised two discussion sessions structured around breakout groups. The groups are listed in Table 3 and Table 4, and synthesis from the discussion points from these breakout sessions is detailed under the Day 3 summary. [Detailed notes from the discussions are also available online.](#)

Discussion session 1 - Topic: BSWG themes and research priorities/gaps.

Four groups were tasked with discussing the following two questions:

- 1) *What is the current “state of the art” in multibeam sonar backscatter research and development, and where are the research gaps?*
- 2) *What do you see as the priority research areas that require attention?*

Breakout groups discussed these questions from 10.30-12:00 (1.5hrs), followed by a 30-minute plenary session where each group reported the main topics covered back to the full group of delegates.

Table 3: Composition of groups for break-out #1

<i>Group A</i>	<i>Group B</i>	<i>Group C</i>	<i>Group D (online)</i>
Craig Brown	Miguel Candido	Xavier Lurton	Qian Bai
Ridha Fezzani	Luciano Fonseca	Peter Porskamp	Aleksandra Kruss
Adriano Fonseca	Claire Haar	Alexandre Schimel	Pim Kuus
Tim LeBas	Vincent Lecours	Mike Smith	Adolfo Lobo
Jens Schneider	Benjamin Misiuk	Jake Tan	Chris McGonigle
Meghan Troupe	Marc Roche		Sebastien Mestdagh
			Iain Parnum
			Anne Sophie Piette
			Patrick Nissen
			Peter Urban

Discussion session 2 - Topic: BSWG direction and structure/organization.

Four groups were tasked with discussing the following three questions:

- 1) *What role should BSWG II play in helping advance the science and the adoption/application of MBES backscatter products by stakeholders?*
- 2) *What role should/can industry play in BSWG II?*

3) How would you like to see the BSWG II move forward into the future?

Breakout groups discussed these questions from 14:00-15:30 (1.5hrs), followed by a 30-minute plenary session where each group reported the main topics covered back to the full group of delegates.

Table 4: Composition of groups for break-out #2

Group A	Group B	Group C	Group D (online)
Craig Brown	Miguel Candido	Xavier Lurton	Qian Bai
Ridha Fezzani	Luciano Fonseca	Peter Porskamp	Pim Kuus
Adriano Fonseca	Claire Haar	Alexandre Schimel	Eric Mallard
Tim LeBas	Vincent Lecours	Mike Smith	Chris McGonigle
Jens Schneider	Benjamin Misiuk	Jake Tan	Sebastien Mestdagh
Emily Sklar	Marc Roche	Meghan Troupe	Anne Sophie Piette
			Peter Urban

Development of a Roadmap for the BSWG (Day 3):

The final day of the workshop comprised plenary discussions to synthesize material and discussion points from the previous 2 days. A summary of the plenary discussion is broken into three main topics, summarized below. More details can be found in the [notes document available online](#).

Topic #1: BSWG mission and objectives

The original mission statement of the BSWG was reviewed (from website <https://geohab.org/backscatter-working-group/>):

“The ultimate intention of the Working Group is that backscatter data acquired from differing systems, or processed through differing software tools, generate consistent values over a same area under the same conditions; and that these data are scientifically meaningful and usable by end-users from various application domains (geoscience, environment, hydrography...).

Within this framework, the purpose of the Working Group is to propose:

- *To users: guidelines or best practice approaches for the acquisition and processing of backscatter data from seafloor-mapping sonars;*
- *To sonar manufacturers and software developers: recommendations for the improvement and further development of systems and processing tools.”*

There was a broad agreement on the following points:

1. The mission statement should be kept general enough so that it does not need to be updated regularly, while objectives can/should be revised on a regular basis.
2. It should include Water-Column Data from now on.
3. Three roles define the mission of BSWG. They are described in Table 5 below:

Table 5: Envisioned roles of the BSWG

<i>Role</i>	<i>Description</i>	<i>Possible tasks fulfilling the role</i>
Educate	Teaching, outreach. Provide an authoritative source of information about backscatter for backscatter users	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Write updated guidelines document (with new chapter on WCD, but not on the novel topic of multispectral backscatter) • Publish special issues • Maintain a Wikipedia-type online source of information • Maintain a discussion/forum platform for users to ask/answer backscatter-related questions
Advise	By gathering members, BSWG has more weight to promote the community goals, direct research, or influence some stakeholders for the benefit of all	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Write and publish “best practices” (standards, protocols) e.g., data acquisition, sonar calibration, processing metadata, backscatter quality, etc. • Maintain and popularise benchmarks. To be established for each type of application e.g.: Network of reference sites for calibration; E-catalogue / Atlas comprising collection of BS case studies; Library of AR signatures; Library of reference files for processing software; Benchmark datasets for specific method development (e.g., detection of gas flares in WCD) • Define and update research gaps and priorities (which researchers can use to justify their proposals)
Network	Agora, community	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Hold regular meetings to bring all stakeholders (academia, government, industry, etc.) together. This will help facilitate communication between all involved parties involved in the collection, processing and ultimately end use of backscatter data. • Be a news source. Diffuse latest updates on ongoing projects, through seminars (or webinars, workshops, conference sessions), or top-down communication (website updates, mailing list, etc.) • Organise active outreach events. e.g., Shallow Survey-type exercises, Hackathons

In response to its three roles, the BSWG mission statement will be updated on the website in the near future.

Topic #2: Standards

It was noted during the meeting that several examples of institutional/national level promoted guidelines exist for acquisition and/or processing of multibeam sonar data, which in the case of backscatter data, reference or draw from past recommendations of the BSWG, most often the BSWG 2015 report (see below) (note: list is not exhaustive):

- Best practice guidelines that include backscatter, e.g. the Australian Multibeam Guidelines: <https://australian-multibeam-guidelines.github.io/> (see Section 3.6 Seafloor backscatter, and Section 3.7 Water column backscatter)
- The Australian Hydro Office has adopted a nomenclature of levels of processing for their data in its Statement of Requirements: https://www.hydro.gov.au/NHP/HIPP_SOR_2022.3.pdf. This approach is similar in inspiration but different from the nomenclature of proposed backscatter levels proposed by Schimel et al. (2018)
- New Zealand survey recommendations:
 - https://www.linz.govt.nz/sites/default/files/understanding_the_value_of_hydrographic_data.pdf
 - <https://www.linz.govt.nz/guidance/marine-information/hydrography/hydrography-standards-and-technical-specifications>
 - https://www.linz.govt.nz/sites/default/files/hyspec_contract-specifications-hydrographic-surveys-v2.0_20200702.pdf

Based on this finding, there was a discussion on the continuation of the advisory role that the BSWG could play in pushing things further by helping to develop and define standards for backscatter calibration, acquisition and quality control. There was consensus that the BSWG is somewhat off defining standards but no clear path to reach this objective has been identified. However, there was agreement that the BSWG has extensive technical and scientific expertise amongst its members, and that it is well placed to work towards defining standards and to promote them in the future. Around this issue, it was pointed out that the settings for acquiring backscatter data are often considered inadequate for the optimal acquisition of bathymetric data. The need for collaboration with official hydrographic bodies is absolutely essential in order to make progress on backscatter standardisation.

Topic #3: BSWG functioning mode and structure (i.e., branches/themes/teams)

As the BSWG is not funded, as before, it will continue to operate on a voluntary basis by its members.

There was agreement that, going forward, the BSWG could be organized as “thematic branches” which would focus on specific sub-topics identified during the workshop, and report back to the BSWG “head”. This would keep the growing BSWG community connected through inter-related topics. Each branch may have a different end-goals, and/or set of activities depending on the focus of the branch, and coordinate their activities on topics of interest to several branches.

Each branch would be led by one or several coordinators whose main roles would include:

- 1) acting as the main point of contact for the branch;
- 2) organising branch meetings to discuss, define, and/or start projects;
- 3) curating a list of BSWG-independent (but relevant) projects, and;
- 4) gathering regular updates and reporting on status up to BSWG head.

Besides the coordinator(s), each branch would also include a short list of active participants whose main roles would include:

- 1) participating in meetings,
- 2) communicating progress on extant or new projects that are underway,
- 3) proposing and/or leading new activities or projects that could be coordinated through the BSWG.

A draft conceptual organizational structure for the BSWG is presented in Figure 1.

Figure 1: Conceptual organizational structure for the BSWG

A table was assembled during the discussion to outline the possible branch topics, possible tasks, and possible coordinators from the workshop participants (Table 6). It should be noted that the number of branches, names, scope, tasks and projects, coordinators and participants may change and evolve once the new structure for the BSWG is more widely communicated with the BSWG community, and the active actors in the community express their intention to actively contribute to BSWG.

Table 6: BSWG Branches, providing initial thoughts on activities and topics to be addressed by each branch, and listing identified "Leads" from the workshop participants

Branch theme	Possible tasks/projects
BSWG Head	<p>Lead(s): Alexandre Schimel, Marc Roche, Craig Brown, Xavier Lurton</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Coordination of meetings (to be determined, but the following are possibilities): <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ BSWG at GeoHab: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Every year as a session within the conference? ▪ Every 4-5 years as a dedicated workshop? ○ Backscatter-focused sessions at relevant conferences (Hydro, Shallow Survey, CHC, IEEE Oceans, etc.).

	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Regular "whole-of-BSWG" meetings, online vs in-person vs hybrid (branches to organise their own meetings to their convenience) ○ Branch leaders to meet regularly? Suggesting a first meeting of branch leaders January 2023 ○ Ideally, record all talks at meetings to put them up on the YouTube channel
Calibration / Manufacturers	<p>Lead(s): Mike Smith, Ridha Fezzani</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Establish a network of backscatter reference sites- ● Define an in-tank calibration protocol for high-frequency systems (e.g., "extended target" by CCOM) – with the goal to provide constructors a practical way to conduct in-factory calibration of their products before delivery. ● Define field calibration procedures (with Acquisition branch). ● Define what is practically "calibration" (e.g., state this is a one-value per beam in dB for combined Tx/Rx), with a standard format (e.g., JSON file?), and how to apply it (e.g., offset to be added to the data, recommend the creation of tools to do it) ● Entice manufacturers to produce acquisition software or data formats that record all ancillary data needed for correction, and provide "BS-friendly" acquisition modes
Acquisition	<p>Lead(s): Jonathan Beaudoin</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Define field calibration procedures (with Calibration branch) ● Define backscatter data quality metrics and standards (see Iskaffe, NGU) ● Define backscatter-friendly acquisition practice standards (what if you need to change settings?) ● Review/contrast existing data collection protocols (AusSeabed, NGU, NIWA, NOAA, USACE, etc.) ● Define standard procedures for the acquisition of data when both bathymetry <u>and</u> backscatter matter ● Define standard procedures for acquisition of multispectral data
Processing	<p>Lead(s): Luciano Fonseca, Alexandre Schimel, Jonathan Beaudoin</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Define set of benchmarking files, e.g., multibeam files such as *.all, *.gsf, *.s7k, with known values, perhaps synthetically created. ● Define set of benchmark sites (ideally as few as possible) where to acquire data with every new sonar model ● Continue project on software intercomparison (BSIP) ● Continue development of methods for harmonisation of multi-source mosaics - turn into a "best practice" doc ● Request example code from manufacturers ● Develop open-source code for processing and interpretation e.g., OpenBST, CoFFee, Ping

	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Although it is best not to change settings of backscatter data acquisition, the reality is that it is often compulsory for bathymetry data acquisition, so it would be good to look at the workflows where there are persistent artefacts due to setting changes (link to Calibration and Acquisition themes). • Standard file format (SONAR-NetCDF4, *.gsf) • Big-data processing (hydrographic services) • Compression algorithms (with WCD branch) • Create a template for BSWG-approved “best practices”: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Standard processing chain (intermediate BL levels) ○ Standard of metadata to accompany backscatter processing products (see Schimel, et al. Mar Geophys Res 39, 121–137 (2018). https://doi.org/10.1007/s11001-018-9341-z)
<p>Analysis and interpretation</p>	<p>Lead(s): Tim Le Bas, Craig Brown</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Segmentation and classification routine comparison • Geoacoustic model benchmarking and understanding what is driving backscatter • Signature catalogue for different seafloor types at different frequencies (the “E-Catalogue”) • Understanding best ancillary (e.g., Sub bottom profiler) and ground truthing techniques • Classification techniques: AI, Machine Learning, Angular response
<p>Environmental effects on BS</p>	<p>Lead(s): Giacomo Montereale Gavazzi, Marc Roche</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Water-column monitoring for impact of in-water scatterers on seabed measurements • BS stability (e.g., seasonal variation), both impact and added value • Impact of direction of surveying (anisotropy/azimuth) • Continue VARIMONIT: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Distil a summary of the VARIMONIT questionnaire that was sent out ○ Send out an excel template file inviting any “Backscatterer” to describe the availability of a serial-BS dataset that could be used to set-up a common exercise: quantifying variability and/or patterns of change using seafloor backscatter ○ Compile inherent papers to make a database ○ Presenting monitoring plans based on BS
<p>WCD</p>	<p>Lead(s): Peter Urban (Note: further discussions with the BSWG WCD group are required)</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Discuss linkage to other branches <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Calibration? Linked to Calibration Branch ○ Acquisition guidelines? Linked to Acquisition Branch ○ Processing tools? Linked to Processing Branch ○ Multispectral? ...Environment? ... ○ Analysis and interpretation (WCD could possibly help in habitat mapping?)

	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Connect with the fishery acoustic community (ICES WGFAST) • Combination/connection with other water column measurement approaches • Write a WCD chapter in an updated guidelines doc <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Relevant research focus: Gas flares, Suspended Particle Matter (SPM) - turbidity (TURBEAMS); Connection to seabed: Benthos (algae)Pockmarks • Compression algorithms (with Processing branch)
Multispectral	<p>Lead(s): Ben Misiuk, Craig Brown</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Write a multispectral chapter in an updated guidelines doc • What applications benefit from multifrequency data? • Use of substrate penetration information derived from separate frequencies/angles. How best/guidance to ground-truth and interpret? • Achievable vs useable frequencies • True broadband (chirp) rather than individual CW frequencies (see experience in fisheries, e.g., EK80)
Communication & Dissemination	<p>Lead(s): Anne Sophie Piette</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Branding: Develop and agree on a final BSWG logo • Website: Stay under the GeoHab website <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Initiate update of the website once the new statements, objectives and BSWG structure are finalized ○ Regular updates with news (e.g., conference special sessions, publications, etc.) • Webmail and mailing list • Dropbox <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Maintain and manage the Dropbox (or similar platform if an alternative is set up)? • Wiki - Consider joining the wiki of the Ocean Mapping Community if this is something we want to pursue • Forum: Develop and maintain a forum for communication by BSWG members • YouTube: Manage and maintain the YouTube channel

Three immediate main projects were also identified during the workshop that generated significant interest, which are not dependent on any of the specific branch activities outlined in the table above, but which are relevant to the wider BSWG community. These are summarized below:

BSWG project #1: Identifying Priorities in Backscatter Research (Leads – Vince Lecours, Vanessa Lucieer, Ben Misiuk, Giacomo Montereale-Gavazzi)

An initiative was launched in September 2022 to conduct an exercise to write and publish a forward-looking peer-reviewed manuscript to help define the priority questions in acoustic backscatter research in the next 5-10 years. The goal of the exercise is to seek and compile expert knowledge and insight which will help to guide the future research agenda for applications and use of acoustic backscatter. This will be based on a Delphi-like online survey of expert opinions, which will then be ranked and synthesised into the research paper.

This effort will be conducted in 5 stages:

Stage 1: Participants submit initial questions (maximum of 3) with a short written justification for each question (50-100 words for each question). Questions must be of broad relevance, answerable through a realistic research design, should not be answerable by a simple Yes or No, and should produce factual, objective answers associated with a measurable outcome.

Stage 2: The lead team will review the questions and if necessary, combine them under themes.

Stage 3: Participants will pick their top five from a complete list of all submitted priority questions (comments are optional).

Stage 4: The lead team will draft the text around the prioritization of questions/themes by participants

Stage 5: Review and comment on the draft manuscript and revisions, as needed and upon request from our lead team.

BSWG project #2: Update the Guidelines document (Lead – Vince Lecours)

There was interest from several participants to assess what updates are required (if any) for the BSWG Guidelines and Recommendations Document that was published by the group in 2015, although there was some reluctance to take on a full revision of the document at this stage. It was agreed a logical first step would be to coordinate a “feasibility/necessity” study over the next 6-12 months to assess what is required. Vince Lecours will lead this action item and reach out to chapter leaders/co-authors to see if they are interested in producing an update, and if/what updates are needed. If gaps/updates are identified these will be discussed at future BSWG meetings to establish how they could be addressed.

BSWG project #3: E-catalogue (Leads – Jens Schneider and Ridha Fezzani)

There was significant interest in developing an E-catalogue. This will require further detailed discussion to fully define the scope, content, and delivery format but would essentially comprise a resource of backscatter examples for the community to access and use. Some of the initial ideas are summarized below:

- Examples showing how good APL modelling can work for calibrated systems and within a homogeneous seafloor, ARC catalogue
- Examples showing examples were APL fails:
 - e.g. when biological BS modulators like fauna, burrowers prevail
 - e.g. when geological modulators like shallow gas, manganese nodules exist
 - e.g. anthropogenic impacts e.g. trawling (sometimes)
 - e.g. subsurface penetration and subsurface layering
- Online, dynamic/interactive map showing reference areas and study sites, with 1-2 pages standardised PDFs describing them (metadata), on BSWG/GeoHab website?
- Reference database

Acknowledgements

The workshop was supported through the Ocean Frontier Institute/Canada First Research Excellence Fund under the research project “Benthic Ecosystem Mapping and Engagement” (www.ofibecome.org).

Appendix: List of Participants

<i>Participant (in-person)</i>	<i>Institution, Country</i>
Craig Brown	Dalhousie University, Canada
Miguel Candido	Portuguese Hydrographic Institute, Portugal
Ridha Fezzani	Ifremer, France
Adriano Fonseca	CCOM/UNH, USA
Luciano Fonseca	University of Brasília, Brazil
Vicki Gazzola	Dalhousie University, Canada
Claire Haar	Dalhousie University, Canada
Ethan Lawler	Dalhousie University, Canada
Tim Le Bas	NOC, UK
Vincent Lecours	UQAC, Canada
Xavier Lurton	Ifremer, France
Benjamin Misiuk	Dalhousie University, Canada
Peter Porskamp	Dalhousie University, Canada
Marc Roche	FPS Economy, Belgium
Alexandre Schimel	NGU, Norway
Jens Schneider	CAU, Germany
Emily Sklar	Dalhousie University, Canada
Mike Smith	CCOM/UNH, USA
Jake Tan	Dalhousie University, Canada
Meghan Troupe	Dalhousie University, Canada

<i>Participant (virtual attendance)</i>	<i>Institution, Country</i>
David Amblas	University of Barcelona, Spain
Qian Bai	TU Delft, Netherlands
Alex Bastos	UFES, Brazil
Jonathan Beaudoin	HydroOctave, Canada
Graeme Bond	CHS, Canada
Samuel Deleu	Flemish Hydrography, Belgium
Massimo Di Stefano	Meteorologisk institutt, Norway
Margaret Dolan	NGU, Norway
Vernon Eville	Dalhousie University, Canada
Peter Feldens	Leibniz Inst, Germany
Daniel Ierodiaconou	Deakin University, Australia
Lukasz Janowski	Gdynia Maritime University, Poland
Aleksandra Kruss	Norbit, Norway
Pim Kuus	Teledyne, UK
Adolfo Lobo	Atlanticland Consulting, Portugal

Eric Maillard	Edgetech, USA
Aniol Marti	DAPCOM Data Services, Spain
Vittorio Maselli	Dalhousie University, Canada
Giuseppe Masetti	CCOM/UNH, USA
Larry Mayer	CCOM/UNH, USA
Chris McGonigle	University of Ulster, Northern Ireland
Pedro Menandro	UFES, Brazil
Sebastien Mestdagh	TU Delft, Netherlands
Giacomo Montereale Gavazzi	Royal Belgian Inst, Belgium
James Muggah	QPS, Canada
Patrick Nissen	Edgetech, USA
Iain Parnum	Curtin University, Australia
Anne Sophie Piette	FPS Economy, Belgium
Natalie Pisciotto	CIDCO, Canada
Jordi Portell de Mora	IEEC Institute of Space Studies of Catalonia, Spain
Justy Siwabessy	Geosciences Australia, Australia
Peter Urban	Ghent University, Belgium
Mario Veleso	GEOMAR, Germany